

Kinetics parameters and sorption of metal ions on newly synthesized chelate forming ion exchange resin

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Salicylic acid is condensed with formaline (37%) under acidic and alkaline conditions using phenol/resorcinol as cross-linking agent to yield chelate resin. Kinetic parameters and sorption of several metal ions as a function of pH, have been studied with a view to use the resin for the separation of such metal ions.

Separation procedure of metal ions using cation exchange resins have been made more selective by the use of complexing agents¹ or by using resins pretreated with chelating agents, but the latter suffer the disadvantage that chelating groups are reversibly fixed in the resin and their displacement during operation can never be avoided. To avoid these difficulties and still take advantage of selectivity of chelating groups, chelate forming resins have been synthesized and their kinetics parameters along with sorption of various metal ions on the resin have been reported.

Results and Discussion

The condensation of salicylic acid with formaldehyde (37%) in acidic media yielded a powdery mass with low moisture content and low base exchange capacity. In basic media, using phenol or resorcinol as a cross-linking agent, red coloured gel was obtained. Resorcinol proved to be a better cross-linking agent than phenol. Base exchange capacity increased with moisture content². Resins containing phenol and resorcinol were found to have base capacity 2.23 and 5.84 mmol/g and moisture content 62.6 and 71.4 %, respectively. These resins were stable in alkali and acid upto 6 N.

Sorption of metal ions at different pH; separation factor : The results of sorption of metal ions on resin studies at different pHs (Table 1) reveal that sorption increases with the increase in pH. The sorption was found to increase in the order : Zn^{II} < Co^{II} < Fe^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II}. The results are in agreement with the reported stability sequence³. The results of cyclic sorption capacity of resorcinol resin for Cu^{II} show that the resin can be used for three cycles with almost no loss in capacity.

The separation factors⁴ for Cu^{II}/Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}/Co^{II}, Cu^{II}/Zn^{II},

Ni^{II}/Co^{II} were found to be 6.80, 10.70, 25.36 and 1.55, respectively, at pH 4. Higher values of separation factor for some binary mixtures of metal ions suggest the possibility of separation using salicylic - formaldehyde - resorcinol chelating resin.

Table 1. Sorption of metal ions at different pHs on salicylic acid-formaldehyde-resorcinol resin (mmol/g of dry resin)

Metal ion	pH Values						
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Ni ^{II}	-	0.024	0.102	0.506	1.080	1.584	1.960
Cu ^{II}	0.018	0.146	0.700	1.470	2.346	2.452	2.420
Co ^{II}	-	-	0.011	0.065	0.273	1.143	2.097
Fe ^{II}	-	0.045	0.092	0.246	-	-	-
Zn ^{II}	-	-	-	0.012	0.199	0.199	0.684

Kinetic parameters : The kinetic equation for an exchange controlled by second order chemical reaction in the limited bath method⁵ is

$$\ln Z = 2 K Q_0 (Q_0 - Q_\infty) t / Q_\infty$$

where, $Z = Q_t(Q_0 - 2 Q_\infty) + Q_0 Q_\infty / Q_t(Q_\infty - Q_t)$

The rate constant (K) is calculate from the slope (S),

$$S = 2 K Q_0 (Q_0 - Q_\infty) / 2.30 Q_\infty$$

where, Q_t is the amount (mmol) of metal ion exchanged in time t , Q_∞ the amount of metal ion exchanged at equilibrium and Q_0 the amount of the chelate resin. In Z vs t should be a linear plot for second order exchange reaction.

The rate of exchange of Cu^{II} ions at different pH was evaluated. The plots of $\ln Z$ vs t for pH values 2, 4, 5 and 6 show linearity, confirming that the exchange rates of Cu^{II} ions with salicylic acid-HCHO chelate resin are of second order. The separate plots indicate that the rate exchange is dependent on pH. The values of different parameters are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Kinetic parameters of exchange rates of Cu^{II}/H on chelating resin
Cu^{II} = 1 × 10⁻³ M, Q₀ = 5.84

Parameter	pH			
	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0
Q _α	0.45	0.700	1.45	2.273
S	0.183	0.270	0.290	0.159
K	9.50 × 10 ⁻⁴	7.24 × 10 ⁻³	1.88 × 10 ⁻³	34.93 × 10 ⁻³

Experimental

Synthesis of resins : A mixture of required quantity of the monomer, NaOH (6 N) and half quantity of formaldehyde (37%) was heated on a water-bath at 60–70° for several hours till the odour of the formaldehyde became feeble. A solution of the required quantity of the cross-linking agent phenol or resorcinol in 6 N NaOH was added to it followed by the remaining half quantity of formaldehyde. Salicylic acid-formaldehyde-phenol resin was prepared by mixing salicylic acid-formaldehyde-phenol and NaOH in molar ratio 1.0 : 2.5 : 1.0 : 1.2, respectively, and salicylic acid-formaldehyde-resorcinol resin was prepared by mixing salicylic acid, formaldehyde, resorcinol and NaOH in the molar ratio 1.0 : 2.2 : 0.8 : 1.5, respectively. It was kept at 60–70° for 3 h, when a reddish brown gel was formed⁶, and further heated for 4 h at 90–100° on a water-bath. The resulting gel was ground and washed with distilled water, then converted to H-form by equilibrating first with 1 N NH₄Cl and then with 1 N KCl solution for 24 h. Moisture content and base exchange capacity of the resin were determined.

Sorption of metal ions : The chelating resin salicylic

acid-formaldehyde-resorcinol having moisture content 71.4% and base exchange capacity 5.84, was used for sorption study of various metal ions (A.R.) at different pHs. Buffer solutions of desired pH were prepared from 0.25 N ammonium acetate and 0.1 N NH₄OH⁷. The resin (1.0 g), freed from surface moisture, was equilibrated with buffer solution (100 ml) of desired pH. The metal ion solution at the same pH was added to it and kept for 24 h with stirring to ensure maximum absorption. The amount of metal ion sorbed was calculated in terms of mmol/g of dry resin.

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